

CovTracer-EN: The Ongoing Journey of Covid-19 Digital Contact Tracing in Cyprus

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Abstract—

I. INTRODUCTION

Contact tracing plays an important role in all phases of a disease outbreak, as part of containment measures during escalation scenarios. Its impact can be boosted by a strategy supporting wider testing of persons being at risk, e.g. living in specific locations, being in close contact to an infected person or showing mild symptoms of the disease. The aim of contact tracing is for public health authorities to rapidly identify as many contacts as confirmed cases of COVID-19, asking them to self-quarantine and avoid infecting other citizens.

The problem of traditional contact tracing is that it is not 100% effective, nor it scales well when the cases of disease increase exponentially. It is not effective because it relies on existing cases to report their close contacts, but those cases might fail to report some encounters (either because they forget or because they intentionally want to hide them from the authorities) or might not be aware of them (e.g. random encounters in common spaces such as supermarkets, restaurants and public transport systems - *hidden infections*). At the same time, traditional contact tracing does not scale well because the capacity of the epidemiological unit of each country is limited and cannot perform the contact tracing tasks adequately after some point.

Thus, digital contact tracing (DCT) is a method to enhance and empower traditional contact tracing, enabling automatic and faster identification and notification of exposed users. The usefulness of DCT has been experimentally observed in various pilots and deployments (see Section II below) and it has mainly been performed via mobile phone apps and the Bluetooth technology. At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemics, GPS was also proposed as a candidate technology for presence tracing, however it was rejected from most

countries for privacy reasons. At the same time, Bluetooth-based DCT mobile apps had some technical issues in countries where they were massively deployed (e.g. Singapore¹ and Australia², e.g. the app not recording contact proximity when idle or security issues [1]). However, after some months, Google and Apple decided to partner together for the first time in their recent history, to develop a Bluetooth-based protocol which tackles the limitations of existing Bluetooth-based DCT apps. They named this protocol Google Apple Exposure Notification (GAEN) API³, allowing one mobile app per country to officially use this protocol.

An important distinction between those DCT GAEN-based mobile apps was the system architecture used, which could be centralized or decentralized [2]. In the centralised case, personal data collected through the mobile apps can be controlled by some governmental authority, such as the PEPP-PT (Pan-European Privacy-Preserving Proximity Tracing) protocol⁴. In the decentralized case, personal data can be controlled by the citizens on their mobile phones, such as the DP-3T (Decentralised Privacy-Preserving Proximity Tracing) protocol [3]. Decentralized approaches are more privacy-preserving, empowering the citizens to take actions themselves. At the same time, they are more complex and require more sophisticated algorithms in place.

Andreas: facts about the usefulness of contact tracing app from the UK, etc.

Christos: Number of GAEN-based apps in EU and around the world, statistics about the use of apps in the EU from the eHealth Network, etc.

II. BACKGROUND & RELATED WORK

Recent studies have indicated that the technique of digital contact tracing based on exposure notifications (EN) via Bluetooth technology works well and offers important benefits for human societies. For example, a pilot at the University of Arizona Arizona, USA [4] showed that the use of an EN app could reduce R(t) by 12%, and would be a significant contribution to transmission control. A modeling study from Google and Oxford University in Washington found that even

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¹<https://www.tracetogether.gov.sg>

²<https://www.health.gov.au/resources/apps-and-tools/covidsafe-app>

³<https://developers.google.com/android/exposure-notifications/exposure-notifications-api>

⁴<https://github.com/pepp-pt/pepp-pt-documentation>

if only 15% of the population uses an EN app, it could lead to a drop in COVID-19 infections and deaths [5]. Further, a study at the Canary Islands, Spain [6] suggested relatively high adherence and compliance as well as a quick turnaround time. The app detected about 6.3 close-contacts per primary simulated infection, a significant percentage being contacts with strangers, although the spontaneous follow-up rate of these notified cases is low. The drawback of the study at the Canaries was the fact that infections were not real but simulated.

– Fundamentals and Enabling Technologies for Social Distancing including contact tracing [7] A survey on frameworks and mobile apps for digital contact tracing is provided in [8], explaining the different technologies and protocols used, the possible security issues and attacks, as well as the decisions taken by each country (mainly European ones) when developing its own national official contact tracing mobile app.

– Emerging Technologies and Open Issues for Social Distancing including contact tracing [9]

– Automatic Contact Tracing Approaches Using Bluetooth Low Energy [10]

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Mention that CovTracer-EN opted for the decentralized approach (it is mentioned in introduction)

A. Outline of the Solution

The high-level architecture of the CovTracer-EN system with the main building blocks is depicted in Figure 1. The coloured blocks comprise CovTracer-EN and are described in more detail hereafter, while the blocks shown in black belong to the wider national and European contact tracing ecosystem and have not been developed as part of CovTracer-EN. The latter include the *SNOW Platform* used by the Ministry of Health (MoH) for managing the positive cases in Cyprus and conducting the traditional contact tracing process and the *European Federation Gateway Service (EFGS)*, which is the pan-European infrastructure deployed in Luxembourg for enabling the cross-border interoperability of the national apps released by various Member States.

The CovTracer-EN system consists of i) the *CovTracer-EN app*, which a light-weight and user-friendly client running on the users' smartphone for triggering notifications upon potential contact with another infected user; ii) the *Backend Server/Database* that collects the diagnosis keys of infected users and distributes them securely to all app users; iii) the *Middleware* that handles the communication between the app and the Backend Server/Database; and iv) the *Verification Server* that is responsible for generating the One-Time-Password (OTP) to enable the infected user to upload his/her diagnosis keys to the Backend Server/Database.

The step-by-step process flow involving these blocks is described in Section III-H.

B. CovTracer-EN Application

The mobile app has been developed both for Android and iOS-based mobile phones, published in Google Play⁵ and Apple Store⁶, respectively.

A minimalist design was followed, considering to include only the important features of EN, facilitating ease of use for as many citizens as possible, irrespective of age and digital skills. The only task required to install the app was to visit the online store of Google or Apple, search for "CovTracer-EN", install the app, run it for once enabling Bluetooth on the phone (plus location for Android phones). The important features of EN were provided in different tabs of the app and included the following:

- Main menu, indicating whether the EN feature was activated or not, explaining to users how to activate in case it was still deactivated (see Figure 2 (a)).
- Menu for uploading the infected keys, in case the user was diagnosed positive to COVID-19. In this case, the user needed to type the OTP sent to him/her as an SMS from the SNOW platform (see Section III-F and Figure 2 (b)).
- Exposure history menu, showing whether the use has been exposed or not. In case of exposure, a notification message appears here, together with advice and guidelines for next steps. We note here that besides the manual *check for exposures*, provided via a button at the bottom of this screen, the app is designed to download automatically infected keys from all around Europe twice a day. In case of exposure, a message appears also in the notification area of the phone's status bar.

Other menus include a *how the app works* animation, where the user follows buttons which show step by step the philosophy of the app, as well as a settings menu, allowing the user to change language (Greek and Turkish as native languages plus English, Russian, French, Arab and Pakistani as languages of minority groups and migrants) or to see policy statement and frequently asked questions (FAQ) with answers.

The *CovTracer-EN App* is based on the open-source GAEN-based mobile application developed by the PathCheck Foundation⁷ in the USA (MIT spin-off) to ensure that the latest updates of the GAEN API are merged in the application codebase as soon as they become available.

C. Backend Server/Database

The *Backend Server* is based on the German open-source Corona-Warn-App (CWA) backend⁸. This ensures that the latest updates with regards to the connectivity of the backend with the EFGS are merged in the backend codebase as soon as they become available.

⁵CovTracer-EN on Google Play, <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=cy.gov.dmid.covtracer>

⁶CovTracer-EN on Apple Store, <https://apps.apple.com/lb/app/covtracer/id1510330601>

⁷PathCheck Foundation. <https://www.pathcheck.org>

⁸Corona-Warn-App, <https://github.com/corona-warn-app>

Fig. 1. Architecture of the CovTracer-EN system. Coloured blocks denote the main building blocks, while blocks in black are part of the wider ecosystem.

Fig. 2. Screenshots of the CovTracer-EN mobile application. (Starting from left) a) Dashboard indicating whether EN feature is activated or not, b) Interface used for uploading infected keys, where the user needs to add an OTP to verify the submission, c) EN history, showing whether the use has been exposed or not, together with advice, d) and e) Explanations of how the app works in general.

Philippos: 1-2 paragraphs with some implementation details, e.g., programming languages, APIs, server infrastructure, etc.

D. Middleware

The *Middleware* manages the communication between the CovTracer-EN mobile application and backend by implementing the required endpoints for the transformation of the PathCheck-CWA messages exchanged between them to the right format. This option offers the flexibility to quickly incorporate any updates, either on the CovTracer-EN application side or the CovTracer-EN backend side, thus reducing the

time for releasing the latest version of the CovTracer-EN application to the public.

DSOS value computation ...

The *Middleware* verifies that the OTP is valid; otherwise, it returns ...

Philippos: 1-2 paragraphs with some implementation details, e.g., programming languages, APIs, etc.

E. Verification Server

The *Verification Server* handles the generation and validation of the 12-digit OTP that is required for a positively-tested

citizen to upload the infected keys to the backend with his/her consent. It is based on an OTP generator developed by the ITI/CERTH Research Center, Greece and is deployed locally in Cyprus alongside the Backend Server.

1-2 paragraphs with some implementation details by KIOS. date of the test, date of symptoms, valid for 24 hours.

F. SNOW Platform

The *SNOW Platform* has been used by the MoH for managing the epidemiological situation in Cyprus by means of keeping the personal information of Cypriot citizens' that have been tested positive. It is used by the epidemiologists for initiating the traditional contact tracing process (i.e., through interview) by contacting the infected citizens.

By sending an OTP via SMS to the citizen at the end of the interview, the citizen may opt to share his/her infected keys and notify other users of the CovTracer-EN application in Cyprus or other EU citizens through their respective national application/backend. Note that no personally identifiable information is exchanged with the CovTracer-EN backend.

Boxes added to the user-interface for CovTRacer-EN.

G. European Federation Gateway Service

Short description of the EFGS for cross-border interoperability and refer to Section IV for more details.

H. Process Flow

The daily operation of the CovTracer-EN system includes the following steps as part of the process flow; see Figure 1.

- **Step 1:** After the traditional contact tracing process through the interview with the positive case, the epidemiology unit at the MoH asks whether he/she has been using the app for some days in the past and if he/she would like to receive an OTP by SMS to submit the infected keys to the system. Upon receiving the user consent, an OTP request is sent to the Verification Server. Note that this OTP request includes two important dates, i.e., the *test date* that the user had his/her lab examination and the *symptoms date* that represents the date since the onset of symptoms, if any.
- **Step 2:** The Verification Server creates a unique 12-digit OTP that encodes the test and symptoms dates and sends it back to the SNOW Platform.
- **Step 3:** The OTP code is appended to an automated SMS that is sent to the user's mobile phone with instructions that the OTP is intended strictly for personal use and expires in 24 hours.
- **Step 4:** The user inserts the OTP into the CoVtracer-EN app and after provision of informed consent he/she submits the infected keys and OTP to the Middleware.
- **Step 5:** The Middleware sends a request to the Verification Server to check the validity of the submitted OTP and ensure that the OTP has not been used already or expired.
- **Step 6:** If the Verification Server confirms that the OTP is valid, then the Middleware computes the DSOS value

Fig. 3. EFGS architecture and connectivity with national backends [11].

for each infected key as described in Section III-D and amends the user keys with the corresponding DSOS values.

- **Step 7:** The Middleware forwards the verified keys to the Backend Server/Database for storing them.
- **Step 8:** After collecting the infected keys by multiple users that correspond to the previous 14 days, the Backend Server/Database prepares all infected keys by packaging them in .zip files pertaining to different day/hour. Subsequently, the .zip files are sent to the Middleware.
- **Step 9:** The Middleware distributes the keys to the app users, either automatically twice per day as part of the periodic check for exposures procedure or manually upon user request, together with the latest configuration file that contains the parameter values set by the epidemiology unit to control the sensitivity of the contact tracing and regulate the volume of the notifications triggered depending on the current situation with the pandemic.
- **Step 10:** As part of the connectivity with the EFGS, the Backend Server uploads to the EFGS multiple times per day the infected keys of CovTracer-EN users to enable EU citizens who are using their national contact tracing apps to receive exposure notifications (triggered by infected Cypriots) after visiting Cyprus.
- **Step 11:** In a similar fashion, the Backend Server downloads the infected keys by EU citizens who have shared them through their national apps that are connected to the EFGS.

IV. CROSS-BORDER INTEROPERABILITY

Philippos: 1-2 paragraph about the EFGS architecture and how we implemented the required endpoints with reference to Figure 3. Some text can be copied from this resource [11].

Philippos: 1-2 paragraph with some details about the security and authentication, e.g., the 2 certificates, etc., with reference to Figure 4 that depicts the data distribution between the EFGS and the national backends. Some text can be copied from this resource [12].

Fig. 4. Data governance model of the EFGS [12].

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Performance Metrics

We report statistics about the performance of CovTracer-EN using the following metrics.

Number of app downloads (N_d): The number of times that the CovTracer-EN app has been downloaded daily based on the absolute numbers exported from the Google Play and Apple App Stores.

Number of active users (N_a): The estimated cumulative number of users who are actively using the CovTracer-EN app. Note that due to the privacy-preserving design of the app it is not possible to compute this accurately unless an analytics engine has been integrated into the system where each device featuring the contact tracing app periodically transmits a “pulse” signal⁹. We estimate this based on the number of *active installs* reported on the Google Play Store, i.e., the number of Android phones that have currently the app installed. Unfortunately, the Apple Store does not provide this statistic. To estimate the number of active iOS devices we take the following approach: We compute the *retention* on Android devices as the ratio of the number of active users to the number of downloads. Based on the retention, the number of active iOS devices can be estimated using the number of downloads from the Apple app store. However, an installed app does not necessarily indicate an active user, i.e., a user whose app is in sync with the Backend to regularly receive the latest infected keys and check for exposures. For this reason, we cross-check N_a with the number of requests received daily at the Backend; it is expected that the number of requests will increase linearly with the

- Baseline statistics shown in Figure 5, e.g., number of app downloads, active users + graphs. Not KPIs and meta-statistics, e.g., about the effectiveness of the app based on the number of notifications, etc.

- Power profile of the app on Android - Stefanos.

VI. LESSONS LEARNED

A. Integration with the Contact Tracing Ecosystem

Integration with the SNOW Platform to preserve user anonymity.

Set the risk calculation parameters with the epidemiologists and decide the user interface of the CovTracer-EN mobile application.

⁹The *Immuni* app released in Italy includes this feature implemented in a fully anonymous fashion.

B. Transparency & Data Privacy

- Decide and formulate the legal basis to process the personal data based on user consent.

- Prepare the documentation regarding the fulfilment of the transparency requirements including a Data Privacy Information Notice (DPIN) detailing the processing in the CovTracer-EN application. This DPIN is provided as a permanent easily accessible resource through the CovTracer-EN official website.

- Consult the office of the Commissioner for Personal Data Protection (CPDP), which is the independent supervisory authority for the protection of the individual in Cyprus. The consultation is with regards to data protection aspects of the CovTracer-EN application and any possible implications after on-boarding the EFGS.

Perform the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and submit for approval to the CPDP.

pseudonymized personal data

Dual user consent for submitting the infected keys both to the CovTracer-EN Backend and Database, as well as uploading them to the EFGS

C. Communication & Promotion

D. Connection with the EFGS

VII. CONCLUSIONS

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Fig. 5. (a) ; (b) ; (c) .

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